

A unified multiscale framework for stress-Based topology optimization using local constraint enforcement

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a robust multiscale formulation for stress-constrained topology optimization aimed at designing lightweight and structurally resilient components. Unlike classical compliance-based methods, which may result in topologies unable to support applied loads, the proposed approach minimizes structural volume while rigorously enforcing local stress constraints. A dual-scale framework integrates macro-structural optimization with periodic micro-structural design, leveraging the Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP) method; though it remains adaptable to other established topology optimization techniques. To address the computational challenges arising from numerous local stress constraints, we implement an Augmented Lagrangian strategy combined with polynomial vanishing constraints, eliminating the need for aggregation functions such as the p-norm or Kreisselmeier-Steinhauser functions. The resulting optimization algorithm is accurate and scalable, supported by a detailed sensitivity analysis and adjoint-based gradient computation. Numerical experiments in two dimensions validate the effectiveness of the method, demonstrating superior stress distribution and structural efficiency compared to classical formulations. This work contributes a comprehensive and scalable methodology for multiscale topology optimization under stress constraints, suitable for high-performance engineering applications.

1. Introduction

The standard formulation of a topology optimization (TO) problem typically involves minimizing structural compliance under a prescribed volume constraint. This compliance-based framework has become a cornerstone in structural optimization due to its ability to generate stiff, material-efficient designs. However, despite its widespread adoption, this formulation presents inherent limitations when it comes to ensuring structural safety under realistic loading scenarios. Specifically, minimizing compliance does not directly control the stress distribution within the structure, nor does it guaranty that local stress limits will not be exceeded [1]. As a result, the optimized topologies produced by this formulation may be prone to failure when subjected to operational loads.

To mitigate this risk, additional stress evaluations are often conducted after the optimization process is over. These assessments frequently reveal regions of high stress concentration or structurally insufficient members, necessitating manual or semi-automated modifications to the optimized design. Such adjustments, while necessary for safety, compromise the optimality of the solution and introduce inefficiencies that could have been avoided if stress constraints had been integrated into the optimization framework from the outset. Moreover, these post-hoc modifications can lead to significant deviations from the original topology, potentially increasing

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the overall volume or altering the load path in ways that reduce the mechanical performance and material efficiency of the structure. Consequently, there is a critical need to reformulate the TO problem in a way that explicitly accounts for stress considerations during the optimization phase.

To design structures that are robust and lightweight, the classical topology optimization formulation must be fundamentally restructured. Rather than minimizing compliance, which indirectly correlates with structural performance, a more effective approach is to directly minimize the total material volume while explicitly incorporating stress constraints. This shift in formulation acknowledges that structural integrity under prescribed loading conditions is paramount and must be embedded within the optimization process itself. By making volume minimization the primary objective, the optimization targets material efficiency. Simultaneously, enforcing local or global stress constraints ensures that the resulting topology remains structurally sound and capable of withstanding operational loads. This reformulation transforms traditional compliance-based optimization into a stress-constrained volume minimization problem-one that more faithfully reflects the dual engineering goals of material economy and structural safety.

In the literature a wide range of formulations have been developed to address the limitations of compliance-based topology optimization through stress integration [2–5]. Among these, a particularly significant approach involves minimizing structural volume while enforcing local stress constraints [5–7]. This study adopts and investigates this framework, in which the classical objective function of compliance is replaced by the total volume of the structure. Concurrently, the traditional volume constraint is replaced by a set of local stress constraints to ensure that material failure does not occur under the prescribed loading conditions.

In this reformulated problem, each finite element in the discretized domain may contribute a separate stress constraint, meaning that the total number of constraints scales directly with the resolution of the finite element mesh. Consequently, the problem becomes considerably more complex and computationally demanding than the classical formulation. The sheer volume of constraints necessitates advanced numerical techniques to manage computational efficiency while maintaining constraint fidelity. Despite this challenge, the integration of stress constraints is essential for generating designs that are not only materially efficient, but also structurally reliable across a broad range of engineering applications.

To address the substantial number of constraints introduced by the incorporation of stress conditions in the optimization domain, various solution strategies have been developed. Among these, the Augmented Lagrangian (AL) method [8,9] has emerged as a particularly effective approach due to its ability to handle multiple constraints without resorting to aggregation techniques, which can obscure the localized nature of stress violations [10,11]. In this study, we adopt the AL framework in combination with polynomial vanishing constraint functions [7], which offer smooth and continuous penalization of constraint violations along with the two scale TO formulation similar to [12–14]. This combination enables efficient handling of constraint enforcement while preserving the gradient consistency required for gradient-based optimization solvers.

The use of the AL method also facilitates adaptive control over constraint satisfaction through the updating of penalty parameters and Lagrange multipliers, thus ensuring convergence to feasible solutions even in highly constrained scenarios. A key novelty of this study lies in integrating this approach within a unified multiscale framework that simultaneously addresses macro- and micro-level stress constraints without relying on aggregation techniques. The strengths of this approach-its robustness, accuracy, and scalability-will be explored in detail in the subsequent sections, where its implementation and performance in multiscale topology optimization problems are thoroughly examined.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. [Section 2](#) reviews recent advances in stress-based topology optimization, highlighting key methodologies and their limitations, and delineates how our proposed framework extends beyond the current state of the art. [Section 3](#) introduces the mathematical formulation of the multiscale topology optimization problem, incorporating both macro- and micro-structural behaviors through a unified augmented Lagrangian framework. [Section 4](#) details the optimization algorithm and the derivation of sensitivity expressions, leveraging the adjoint method for computational efficiency. In [Section 5](#), we present a series of numerical experiments in two- and three-dimensional settings to validate the performance and versatility of the proposed approach. Finally, [Section 6](#) summarizes the main contributions and provides directions for future research.

For readability, the principal symbols used throughout the paper are collected in [Table 3.4.0.1](#). Symbols are defined upon first use and reused consistently across [Sections 2](#) to [4](#).

2. Recent advances in stress-Based topology optimization

To effectively address the stress-based TO problem with volume minimization, two predominant methodological approaches have emerged in the literature. The first involves the use of constraint aggregation techniques, while the second centers on the application of the AL framework. The principal challenge in this class of problems lies in the vast number of local stress constraints, which are applied to individual elements within the finite element mesh. This results in a high-dimensional constraint space that significantly increases the computational burden of the optimization process.

2.1. Constraint aggregation techniques for stress reduction

This subsection would perform a brief presentation on the use of aggregation functions such as the p -norm and Kreisselmeier-Steinhauser (KS) function to consolidate numerous local stress constraints into manageable forms, allowing efficient optimization without compromising the fidelity of the stress constraint.

To mitigate this complexity, aggregation-based methods have been proposed to reduce the dimensionality of the constraint set. These techniques group local stress constraints into a smaller number of representative clusters or aggregate measures, which are then

enforced during optimization. Among the most widely used aggregation functions are the p -norm function [15] and the Kreisselmeier-Steinhauser (KS) function [16]. These functions provide smooth and differentiable approximations of maximum stress, enabling the use of efficient gradient-based optimization algorithms while maintaining a tractable number of constraints.

Yang and Chen [17], identified two key challenges in the stress based TO problem. The first challenge concerned the enormous number of element-wise constraints and the second challenge concerned the nonlinear stress to design relations. To explore the implications of these challenges, they conducted a series of numerical experiments applying both the Kreisselmeier-Steinhauser (KS) and the p -norm functions as stress aggregation techniques. Le et al. [18] further advanced the discussion by identifying a third challenge. They introduced the phenomenon of stress singularities. This phenomenon occurs when non-negligible stress values persist in regions where the material density approaches zero. Such anomalies are physically inconsistent and numerically problematic, as they distort the true stress state and can mislead the optimization algorithm. To address this issue, Le et al. proposed the use of relaxation techniques aimed at regularizing stress evaluations in low-density regions. Lee et al. [19] extended the p -norm aggregation to dependent loading conditions, enabling efficient constraint handling without sacrificing localized stress control. Luo et al. [20] refined the KS aggregation function by introducing a reduction parameter that provided enhanced flexibility in shaping the aggregation curve. Holmberg et al. [21] proposed a clustering-based approach in combination with a modified p -norm function to manage stress constraints more effectively. Extending the use of aggregation functions to specialized applications, De Leon et al. [2] applied the p -norm strategy in the context of compliant mechanism design. Further innovation was introduced by Kiyono et al. [3], who developed a multi- p -norm formulation where multiple values of the exponent p were utilized concurrently. Further refinements to stress aggregation techniques have been proposed to address the inherent limitations of traditional p -norm formulations. Lee et al. [4] introduced a correction method for the p -norm approach, which leverages the lower bound characteristics of the stress response curve. Building on the idea of hybrid objectives, Lian et al. [22] proposed a combined formulation in which both compliance and stress constraints are integrated into a unified objective function. The stress field was aggregated using the p -norm, allowing simultaneous control of structural stiffness and stress distribution. In a distinct yet complementary direction, Liu et al. [23] extended the application of stress-based topology optimization to more complex geometries by employing isogeometric analysis (IGA).

Across the previously discussed literature, the Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP) method has been the predominant interpolation strategy for modeling material density distribution. However, alternative methodologies have also emerged to address the specific limitations of SIMP-based formulations. In particular, Xia et al. [24] introduced a stress-based topology optimization framework using the Bi-directional Evolutionary Structural Optimization (BESO) method. Their approach focused on minimizing structural stress under a prescribed volume constraint and incorporated a p -norm function to aggregate local stress constraints. Building on this advancement, Fan et al. [25] extended the BESO strategy to concurrently optimize compliance and stress. Their formulation introduced the p -norm of the stress field directly into the objective function. Notably, they proposed a progressive increase in the exponent p once the volume constraint was satisfied, enabling the optimizer to shift focus toward fine-tuning the stress field in later stages of the optimization.

2.2. Augmented lagrangian methods for local constraint enforcement

This subsection would focus on the direct handling of individual stress constraints using the Augmented Lagrangian framework. It would emphasize how this method circumvents the need for aggregation and offers improved accuracy and flexibility in constraint management.

Despite their widespread adoption, clustering and aggregation-based approaches for stress-constrained topology optimization have shown significant limitations, particularly in satisfying stress constraints uniformly throughout the design domain. One of the major drawbacks of these techniques is their tendency to overlook localized stress violations, especially in regions not well captured by the aggregated representation. This can lead to optimized topologies that, while theoretically feasible, may fail under actual loading conditions due to unaccounted-for stress concentrations.

To overcome this fundamental limitation, aggregation-free formulations based on the Augmented Lagrangian method have gained traction. As established in the foundational works of Bertsekas [8,26], the AL framework enables the incorporation of local stress constraints directly into the objective function through a penalty-based formulation. This method circumvents the need for constraint aggregation by assigning individual penalty terms to each local constraint, thereby maintaining fidelity to the original stress distribution. A key advantage of the AL-based approach lies in its computational efficiency—specifically, the requirement of only a single adjoint vector for sensitivity analysis, regardless of the number of local stress constraints. This significantly reduces computational overhead while preserving accuracy.

Pereira et al. [27] utilized the AL function within a density-based optimization framework to address stress constraints effectively. Further advancements were presented by Emmendoerfer and Fancello [28,29], who integrated the AL approach with the level-set method, enhancing boundary representation and interface tracking. Similarly, James et al. [30] proposed a hybrid methodology wherein the AL function was applied to the volume constraint, while stress constraints were still aggregated using a p -norm function. Senhora et al. [6] advanced the application of the AL method in stress-constrained topology optimization by developing a SIMP-based formulation that incorporates piecewise vanishing constraints. Building upon this foundational work, Giraldo-Londono and Paulino proposed further methodological advancements in two subsequent studies. In their 2020 paper [5], they introduced a unified AL-based topology optimization framework capable of accommodating various failure criteria beyond von Mises stress. Subsequently, Giraldo-Londono and Paulino released an open-source MATLAB implementation named PolyStress [7]. This tool extends the functionality of the well-known PolyTop code, originally designed for classical compliance-based topology optimization, to support stress-constrained volume minimization problems.

Zhao et al. [31] introduced a concurrent topology optimization framework targeting the stress-constrained design of structures composed of cellular materials. Their formulation was grounded in the SIMP interpolation scheme and employed a periodically repeated unit cell geometry distributed uniformly across the entire design domain. Wei et al. [32] proposed a concurrent multiscale topology optimization (MTO) framework tailored for the design of hierarchical structures with enhanced stress performance. Their approach integrated clustering techniques—specifically the k-means algorithm—as a strategy to reduce the dimensionality of the design space while preserving critical structural details. Ho and Kim [33] introduced a level set-based approach to address stress-constrained two-scale topology optimization problems. Their method employed trimmed quadrilateral meshes generated via level set functions, enabling the accurate representation of evolving structural boundaries without the need for re-meshing. In all the approaches of stress constraint concurrent topology optimization, the basis for the connection of the two scales was the homogenization theory described in [34,35].

2.3. Beyond the state of the art: Contributions of the present work

While prior research has significantly advanced stress-based topology optimization, particularly through constraint aggregation techniques, augmented Lagrangian formulations, and the implementation of vanishing constraints, notable limitations persist. These include inadequate enforcement of local stress constraints, limited integration of multiscale material behaviors, and insufficiently generalized sensitivity formulations that hamper scalability and robustness.

This work introduces a multiscale aggregation-free stress-constrained TO framework that simultaneously resolves macro- and micro-structural design objectives through a concurrent optimization scheme. Unlike conventional methods that treat the material microstructure separately or assume homogenized behavior, our formulation embeds periodic unit cells within each finite element and implements an aggregation-free approach to deal with the large number of stress constraints. This enables a direct linkage between macroscopic loading conditions and microscopic stress fields, thus capturing scale-bridging mechanical interactions more accurately.

The novelty of our approach lies in the precise enforcement of local stress constraints using a non-aggregated AL formulation paired with polynomial vanishing constraints. This combination ensures that only active constraints are penalized, which improves numerical stability and reduces computational overhead. Furthermore, the sensitivity analysis is systematically derived using an adjoint-based framework that decouples displacement sensitivities from design variables. This feature allows the computation of gradients with a single adjoint solve, regardless of the number of local stress constraints, thereby enhancing computational efficiency.

In summary, this work contributes to the advancement of the field by presenting a unified multiscale framework that combines existing techniques in a novel and cohesive manner:

- It integrates microstructural mechanics into stress-constrained topology optimization through a concurrent multiscale formulation;
- It incorporates a refined Augmented Lagrangian method and polynomial vanishing constraints to enforce local stress constraints without relying on aggregation;
- It extends adjoint-based sensitivity analysis to handle both macro and micro design variables within a scalable optimization scheme.

The innovative contribution lies in the systematic integration of these components into a single coherent framework capable of accurately capturing multiscale stress behavior under strict local constraints.

3. Multiscale formulation of stress-Constrained topology optimization

In this section, we present a unified formulation of the multiscale stress-constrained topology optimization problem. The proposed framework concurrently integrates both macro and micro scale behaviors through a single, coherent optimization formulation by embedding periodic unit cells within each finite element of the macrostructure. This unified approach enables the consistent enforcement of local stress constraints at the microscale while guiding the overall structural design toward volume minimization at the macroscale. Unlike traditional multiscale formulations that decouple macro and micro responses, our method ensures strong coupling between scales through shared design variables and constraint evaluations. To efficiently address the large number of local constraints without relying on stress aggregation techniques, we employ the AL approach, augmented by an adjoint-based sensitivity analysis applicable to both scales. Although the mathematical implementation of this methodology allows the unit cell geometry to change at different parts of the macroscale, in this work, a single unit cell is applied for the whole macroscale. This decision was made to simplify and reduce the computational cost of allowing for varying unit cell geometries inside the macroscale geometry. The following subsections provide the complete mathematical formulation, detail the construction of local stress constraints and stress evaluation procedures, and derive the sensitivities required for gradient-based optimization.

3.1. Mathematical problem statement

The mathematical formulation of the multiscale stress-based Topology Optimization problem is given by the expression of Eq. (1):

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_{x,y} V(x, y) \\
 & \text{s.t.} \\
 & g_e(x, y) \leq 0 \\
 & \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \cdot \mathbf{U} \\
 & x_e^{\min} \leq x_e \leq x_e^{\max} \\
 & y_{el}^{\min} \leq y_{el} \leq y_{el}^{\max}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The variables x, y denote the material density vectors of the macro and micro structure, respectively. The design variables x_e and y_{el} represent the material densities associated with the macrostructure and microstructural elements, respectively, where the e and el indices denote the finite elements on macro and micro scales. V denotes the total material volume of the structure, g_e represents the set of local stress constraints applied at the finite element level e of the macro-scale, and $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \cdot \mathbf{U}$ corresponds to the equilibrium equation. Vector \mathbf{F} denotes the loading vector applied at the macro-scale, $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ denotes the global stiffness matrix of the macro-scale, which is a function of both material densities x & y and \mathbf{U} denotes the displacement field of the macro-scale. The bounds x^{\min}, x^{\max} and y^{\min}, y^{\max} define the admissible range of material densities for the respective scales. The following subsections describe the formulation of local stress constraints and the coupling strategy between macro- and micro-level stress fields. The loading conditions are applied on the macroscale and then transferred using the homogenization method to the microscale where the stress field is computed and the yield check is performed.

The global stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} is constructed from the local stiffness matrices of the macro domain k_e . The local stiffness matrices are calculated following the classic homogenization based approach of the following expression.

$$\mathbf{k}_e(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = m_e(x) \cdot \mathbf{k}_e^H(\mathbf{y}) \tag{2}$$

Where the term $m_e(x)$ denotes the influence of the relative material density x_e and matrix $\mathbf{k}_e^H(\mathbf{y})$ denotes the homogenized element stiffness matrix. The equation of term $m_e(x)$ is provided in the next section. The homogenized element stiffness matrix in the case of 2D design space can be computed using the expression of a Q4 finite element stiffness matrix as follows.

$$\mathbf{k}_e^H(\mathbf{y}) = \int_{V_e} (\mathbf{B}_e^T \cdot \mathbf{C}_e^H(\mathbf{y}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e) dV_e \tag{3}$$

Where the term \mathbf{B}_e denotes the strain-displacement matrix, matrix \mathbf{C}_e^H denotes the homogenized elasticity tensor and V_e denotes the volume of element e . The homogenized elasticity tensor \mathbf{C}^H is calculated following the homogenization theory presented in [35], the expression of Eq. (4).

$$\mathbf{C}^H(\mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{V_{el}} \sum_{el=1}^{n_{el}} \int_{V_{el}} (\mathbf{u}_{el}^0 - \mathbf{u}_{el}) \cdot \mathbf{k}_{el}(\mathbf{y}) \cdot (\mathbf{u}_{el}^0 - \mathbf{u}_{el}) dV_{el} \tag{4}$$

Where V_{el} denotes the volume, \mathbf{u}_{el}^0 denotes the displacement field resulting from the application of globally applied unit strains, \mathbf{u}_{el} denotes the displacement field resulting from locally applied unit strains as described by homogenization theory. The term $\mathbf{k}_{el}(\mathbf{y})$ denotes the local stiffness matrix of micro element el . The formulation of the local stiffness matrix k_{el} is based on the calculation of the elasticity tensor C_{el} . The detailed description of the computation of the elasticity tensor is presented in the following subsection 3.3.

Based on the assembly of the global stiffness matrix K and the solution of the equilibrium equation $F = K \cdot U$, the strain field of each element e of the macro scale is simply calculated following the expression.

$$\epsilon_e = \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \mathbf{U}_e \tag{5}$$

This strain field is then used as the basis for the calculation of the strain-stress field of the micro scale, as described in the next subsections.

3.2. Local stress constraint characterization

The implementation of the local stress constraint in this work builds upon the methodology proposed by Giraldo-Londono and Paulino [7]. However, a key distinction lies in the scale at which the stress evaluation is performed. While their formulation computes stresses at the macroscale, the present work introduces a significant advancement by evaluating stresses at the *microscale*, within the periodic unit cells embedded in each macro element. This shift enables a more accurate representation of stress distributions that reflect material heterogeneity and localized effects, which are critical in multiscale structures. The original stress constraint in [7] followed the expression:

$$g_e = m_e(x) \cdot \Lambda_e^3 + \Lambda_e \tag{6}$$

Fig. 1. Polynomial vanishing constraint.

This formulation is focused on the one scale stress based TO problem. Similarly to the original formulation, in the two scale formulation the stress constraint associated with each macro finite element e is denoted by g_e and is defined by the following expression:

$$g_e = m_e(x) \cdot \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} (\Lambda_{el}^3 + \Lambda_{el}) / N_{el} \tag{7}$$

where N_{el} denotes the number of finite elements discretizing the microstructural domain, m_e represents the penalized material density obtained via the SIMP interpolation at the macroscale, and Λ_{el} corresponds to the von Mises stress ratio evaluated at the microscale element level. The evaluation of the stress field under the von Mises yield criterion is conducted under the assumption that the stress magnitudes in the macrostructural elements are lower than those in the microstructural constituents. Consequently, the stress-related component of the constraint function is evaluated at the microscale level, specifically tailored to each macro finite element e . This localized microscale stress computation enables a more accurate enforcement of the stress constraint, reflecting the heterogeneous behavior of the underlying material architecture.

The original introduction of the polynomial vanishing constraint in [7] had the form $g_e = \Lambda_e^3 + \Lambda_e$, in which the term Λ_e was calculated from the stress field of the macroscale. In our implementation, due to the introduction of the two scale problem and the evaluation of the stress field on the micro scale, the original polynomial vanishing constraint was modified according to Eq. (7). The form of this type of constraint ensures that when the constraint is highly violated, the constraint scales to large values. A graphical representation of the polynomial vanishing constraint is presented in Fig. 1.

The term m_e is defined following the expression introduced in [7] and according to the SIMP interpolation scheme applied to the macro domain, and is given below:

$$m_e(x) = x_{min} + x_e^p \cdot (1 - x_{min}) \tag{8}$$

where x_{min} denotes the minimum admissible value for the material density x , and p is the penalization exponent used in the SIMP interpolation scheme to promote discrete material distributions. Although the intermediate values of the term m_e do not have physical meaning, by implementing the SIMP interpolation scheme, the final geometry will mainly have material density values of 0 or 1.

3.3. Coupling macro and micro stress fields

The coupling between the macro- and microstructural stress fields is achieved through a homogenization-based strategy that utilizes the macroscopic strain field to drive the local response of the microstructure. Specifically, the strain field at the microscale is derived from the macroscopic strain distribution, assuming periodic boundary conditions within each representative unit cell. This hierarchical relationship ensures that microstructural stress responses are directly influenced by the global loading state, enabling a consistent and physically meaningful interaction between scales. In Fig. 2, the connection of the two scales through the strain fields is schematically displayed.

The strain field of the porous domain ϵ_e is transformed into the strain field of the periodic unit cell using the asymptotic homogenization technique [36] expressed as follows:

$$\epsilon_{el} = \epsilon_e + \epsilon_{el}^H \tag{9}$$

where ϵ_{el} denotes the strain field in the microstructural element el , ϵ_e is the macroscopic strain vector evaluated at the centroid of the corresponding macro element e , and ϵ_{el}^H represents the periodic strain component resulting from the periodic displacement field. The periodic displacement field is obtained by solving a homogenization problem in the representative unit cell, using the macroscopic strain vector ϵ_e as the imposed loading condition. Consequently, Eq. (9) can be equivalently reformulated as shown in the following expression:

$$\epsilon_{el} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \chi) \cdot \epsilon_e \tag{10}$$

Fig. 2. schematic representation of the macro and micro scales.

where \mathbf{I} denotes the second-order identity matrix, \mathbf{B}_{el} is the strain-displacement matrix associated with the microstructural element el , and χ represents the periodic fluctuation component of the microstructural displacement field. The corresponding stress field on the microscale is then computed based on the strain field derived in Eq. (9), following the constitutive relation expressed in Eq. (11):

$$\sigma_{el} = \mathbf{C}_{el} \cdot \epsilon_{el} \tag{11}$$

where \mathbf{C}_{el} denotes the elasticity tensor of the microstructural element el , characterizing its constitutive mechanical behavior. This tensor encapsulates the stiffness properties of the material and is constructed using the element-specific Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio. The explicit formulation of \mathbf{C}_{el} is provided in Eq. (12):

$$\mathbf{C}_{el} = E_{el} \cdot \mathbf{C}^0 \tag{12}$$

The Young's modulus of each microstructural element el is computed using the Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP) interpolation scheme, adapted for the microscale domain. This approach allows for a continuous variation of stiffness based on the element's material density, promoting a clear distinction between solid and void regions. Consequently, the Young's modulus for each element el is defined by the expression given in Eq. (13):

$$E_{el} = E_{min} + y_{el}^p \cdot (E^0 - E_{min}) \tag{13}$$

where E^0 denotes the Young's modulus of the solid material and E_{min} represents a small positive lower bound introduced to prevent numerical singularities in regions approaching the void. The von Mises equivalent stress, used as the yield criterion for the stress constraint evaluation, is computed from the Cauchy stress components based on the relation provided in Eq. (14):

$$\sigma_{el}^V = \sqrt{\sigma_{el}^T \cdot \mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \sigma_{el}} \tag{14}$$

where σ_{el} represents the Cauchy stress tensor, which encapsulates the internal stress state of the material at the microscale. The individual components of σ_{el} are calculated using the constitutive relation and the strain field, as expressed in Eq. (15):

$$\sigma_{el} = [\sigma_{el}^{11}, \sigma_{el}^{22}, \sigma_{el}^{12}]^T \tag{15}$$

and \mathbf{V}_0 is a scaling matrix that appears in the stress evaluation formulation, defined explicitly in Eq. (16):

$$\mathbf{V}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1/2 & 0 \\ -1/2 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \tag{16}$$

The stress constraint ratio Λ_{el} is calculated based on the expression provided in Eq. (17):

$$\Lambda_{el} = \frac{\sigma_{el}^V}{\sigma_{lim}} - 1 \tag{17}$$

where σ_{el}^V denotes the von Mises equivalent stress and σ_{lim} represents the admissible stress limit for the material at the micro level.

3.3.0.1. On scale separation and modeling error: Our formulation uses first-order computational homogenization with periodic unit cells embedded in each macro element. While this approach is formally asymptotically consistent under strict scale separation, in practice the unit-cell size in our benchmarks is on the order of $1/10$ – $1/30$ of the domain. This may induce boundary-layer effects and local discrepancies in stress predictions relative to a fully resolved (DNS) microstructure, particularly near geometric boundaries and in regions with large strain gradients. Global responses (e.g., displacements and overall stiffness) are typically less sensitive, whereas peak local stresses are more so. To reduce modeling error, we use periodic boundary conditions in the RVE and consistent length-scale control via density filters; in addition, we enforce stress constraints at the microscale, which tends to be conservative. Future extensions could incorporate oversampling/nonlocal schemes or higher-order homogenization to mitigate boundary effects.

3.4. Augmented lagrangian formulation for local stress constraints

To address the challenge posed by the large number of local stress constraints g_e , the Augmented Lagrangian method is adopted. This approach enables the treatment of individual stress constraints without resorting to global aggregation techniques, thus preserving the fidelity of local stress evaluations. The implementation of the AL framework in this work builds upon the methodology introduced in [7], with modifications adapted to the multiscale setting. The general form of the AL functional used in this formulation is given by Eq. (18):

$$\mathcal{L}(x, y, \lambda) = V(x, y) + \frac{1}{N} \cdot P(x, y, \lambda) \quad (18)$$

where N denotes the total number of finite elements in the macrostructural domain. The penalty term P , which enforces the satisfaction of local stress constraints, is computed according to the formulation provided in Eq. (19):

$$P(x, y, \lambda) = \sum_{e=1}^N \left[\lambda_e^k \cdot h_e(x, y) + \frac{\mu^k}{2} \cdot h_e(x, y)^2 \right] \quad (19)$$

where λ and μ denote the Lagrange multipliers and the quadratic penalty parameter, respectively, and h represents the reformulation of the equality constraint derived from the original stress constraint g .

The equality constraint h is formulated as a function of the stress constraint g and the associated Lagrange multipliers. This transformation enables the AL method to enforce the original inequality constraint in a smooth and differentiable manner, as expressed in Eq. (20):

$$h_e^k(x, y) = \max \left[g_e(x, y), -\frac{\lambda_e^k}{\mu^k} \right] \quad (20)$$

For a detailed explanation of the h expression in Eq. (20), the reader is referred to the works of Senhora et al. in [6]. The penalty parameter μ is a positive-definite scalar ($\mu > 0$), applied uniformly across all local constraints. Its value is dynamically updated during the optimization process according to the rule defined in Eq. (21):

$$\mu^{k+1} = \min [\alpha \cdot \mu^k, \mu_{max}] \quad (21)$$

where α is a user-defined update factor greater than one, controlling the rate of increase of the penalty parameter, and μ_{max} specifies the upper bound to which μ can grow. The Lagrange multiplier λ is iteratively updated based on the rule defined in Eq. (22):

$$\lambda_e^{k+1} = \lambda_e^k + \mu^k \cdot h_e(x, y) \quad (22)$$

3.4.0.1. Notation and conventions. We adopt the standard finite-element notation: scalars are italic, vectors and matrices are upright (e.g. \mathbf{U} , \mathbf{F} , \mathbf{K}), and $(\cdot)^T$ denotes transpose. The Macro-element indices use $e = 1, \dots, N$; the micro-element indices (unit-cells) use $el = 1, \dots, N_{el}$. The operator $\max(\cdot, \cdot)$ is applied componentwise when used on vectors. Unless noted, elasticity is linear and small-strain; plane stress/strain assumptions are stated in the problem setup. The main symbols are summarized in Table 3.4.0.1 and are referenced in Eqs. (1)-(20) and in the sensitivity derivations of Section 4.

4. Multiscale gradient derivation for stress-Constrained topology optimization

As in Section 3, we use the symbols listed in Table 3.4.0.1 without redefinition. Gradients are taken with respect to the design variables $x = \{x_e\}$ and $y = \{y_{el}\}$, and depend on the state \mathbf{U} and the adjoint ξ as detailed below.

This section presents the detailed derivation of sensitivity expressions required for the gradient-based optimization of the proposed multiscale stress-constrained topology optimization framework. Specifically, it addresses the sensitivities of local constraint functions g and the augmented lagrangian function, which integrates both volume minimization and stress constraint penalties. To manage the computational complexity arising from the coupled macro- and microscale formulations, the adjoint method is employed, effectively decoupling the displacement sensitivities and enabling efficient gradient computation. Due to the hierarchical nature of the multiscale formulation and the incorporation of local stress constraints, the sensitivity analysis outlined herein is novel and structurally distinct from classical single-scale formulations. This tailored approach enables a unified treatment of sensitivities across scales, facilitating accurate and computationally efficient design updates.

Table 1

Notation used in the multiscale stress-constrained topology optimization framework.

Symbol	Definition
e, N	Macro finite element index; number of macro elements
el, N_{el}	Micro (unit-cell) element index; elements per unit cell
$x_e \in [x^{\min}, x^{\max}]$	Macro design variable (density) for element e
$y_{el} \in [y^{\min}, y^{\max}]$	Micro design variable (density) for micro element el
$m_e(x)$	Penalized macro density (SIMP): $x_{\min} + x_e^p(1 - x_{\min})$ (8)
$E_{el}(y)$	Micro Young's modulus (SIMP): $E_{\min} + y_{el}^p(E^0 - E_{\min})$ (13)
C^0, C_{el}	Reference elasticity tensor; micro element tensor $E_{el}C^0$ (12)
$K(x, y)$	Global stiffness matrix assembled from macro/micro contributions
U, F	Displacement and load vectors; $KU = F$ (1)
B_e, B_{el}	Macro and micro strain-displacement matrices
ϵ_e	Macro strain in element e ($\epsilon_e = B_e U$)
χ	Periodic fluctuation field from unit-cell problems
ϵ_{el}	Micro strain: $(I - B_{el}\chi)\epsilon_e$ (10)
σ_{el}	Micro Cauchy stress: $C_{el}\epsilon_{el}$ (11)
V_0	Matrix for von Mises evaluation (16)
σ_{el}^V	Micro von Mises equivalent stress $\sqrt{\sigma_{el}^T V_0 \sigma_{el}}$ (14)
σ_{lim}	Allowable stress limit (material property)
Λ_{el}	Stress ratio at micro element: $\sigma_{el}^V / \sigma_{\text{lim}} - 1$ (17)
g_e	Local stress constraint for macro element e (7)
h_e	AL equality transform of g_e (20)
λ_e, μ	Lagrange multiplier and penalty parameter (AL) (19), (22), (21)
$\mathcal{L}(x, y, \lambda)$	Augmented Lagrangian functional (18)
ξ	Adjoint vector solving $K^T \xi = b$ (33), (42)
$V(x, y)$	Total material volume (objective)
A_e, A_{el}	Areas of macro and micro elements (for volume sensitivities) (24), (25)
p	SIMP penalization exponent (macro and micro)
x_{\min}, E_{\min}, E^0	Minimum macro density; minimum modulus; solid modulus
$\text{tol}, \epsilon_{\text{obj}}, \epsilon_{\text{feas}}$	Generic tolerances; objective and feasibility tolerances

4.1. Sensitivity derivation for augmented lagrangian

The sensitivity of the Augmented Lagrangian function is obtained separately for the x and y sets of design variables. For each set, the sensitivity of the AL function is based on the expression of Eq. (23).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial x_e} &= \frac{\partial V}{\partial x_e} + 1/N \cdot \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_e} \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial y_{el}} &= \frac{\partial V}{\partial y_{el}} + 1/N \cdot \frac{\partial P}{\partial y_{el}} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

In the next subsections, an explanation for the sensitivities of both the volume and penalty function is provided in detail.

4.1.1. Volume sensitivity components

In this subsection, the expressions for volume sensitivities with respect to both sets of design variables are presented. These terms define the gradient of the objective function component associated with material usage.

The volume sensitivity with respect to the macro material densities $\partial V / \partial x_e$ is obtained following the expression of Eq. (24)

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial x_e} = \frac{A_e}{\sum_{e=1}^{N_e} A_e} \quad (24)$$

Similarly, volume sensitivity with respect to micro material densities $\partial V / \partial y_{el}$ is obtained following the expression of Eq. (25).

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial y_{el}} = \frac{A_{el}}{\sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} A_{el}} \quad (25)$$

where A_e refers to the area of each finite element e and A_{el} refers to the area of each finite element el .

4.1.2. Penalty function gradients with respect to design variables

In this subsection, the sensitivities of the stress penalty term are provided, capturing how changes in design variables influence constraint violations. These are weighted by Lagrange multipliers and penalty coefficients. The adjoint equation is also introduced to isolate and remove the sensitivity terms that depend on the structural displacement field. This step is critical for an efficient implementation.

Regarding the sensitivity of the penalty function P with respect to the material densities x , the term $\partial P/\partial x_e$ is obtained following the expression of Eq. (26).

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_e} = (\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot \frac{\partial h}{\partial x_e} \quad (26)$$

where the term $\partial h/\partial x_e$ is equal to the sensitivity of the constraint function g_e when the value of g_e is greater than $-\Lambda_e/\mu$. The detailed presentation of the sensitivity of the constraint function g_e is presented in Fig. A. In this case, the term $\partial h/\partial x_e$ is obtained following the expression of Eq. (27).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x_e} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial x_e} = \frac{\partial m}{\partial x_e} \cdot \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} \frac{\Lambda_{el}^3 + \Lambda_{el}}{N_{el}} \\ + m_e(x) \cdot \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} \left((3 \cdot \Lambda_{el}^2 + 1) \cdot \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial x_e} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{N_{el}} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

where, the term $\partial \Lambda/\partial x_e$ is obtained by following the expression of Eq. (28).

$$\frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial x_e} = \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{el}}{\sigma_{el}^V} \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C}_{el} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial x_e} \quad (28)$$

To remove the term $\partial \mathbf{U}/\partial x_e$, the adjoint method is implemented. Using the adjoint method, the penalty function is formulated following the expression of Eq. (29).

$$P(x, y, \lambda) = \sum_{e=1}^N \left[\lambda_e^k \cdot h_e(x, y) + \frac{\mu^k}{2} \cdot h_e(x, y)^2 \right] + \xi \cdot (\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U} - \mathbf{F}) \quad (29)$$

The sensitivity of the penalty function follows the expression of Eq. (30).

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_e} = [\lambda_e^k + \mu^k \cdot h_e(x)] \cdot \frac{\partial h}{\partial x_e} + \xi \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial x_e} \cdot \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{K} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial x_e} \right) \quad (30)$$

By replacing the term $\partial h/\partial x_e$, Eq. (29) is expanded following the expression of Eq. (31).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_e} = (\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot \left[\right. \\ \frac{\partial m}{\partial x_e} \cdot \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} \frac{\Lambda_{el}^3 + \Lambda_{el}}{N_{el}} \\ + m_e(x) \cdot \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} \left((3 \cdot \Lambda_{el}^2 + 1) \cdot \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{el}}{\sigma_{el}^V} \right. \\ \left. \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C}_{el} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial x_e} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{N_{el}} \left. \right] \\ + \xi \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial x_e} \cdot \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{K} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial x_e} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Rearranging the terms of Eq. (31), part of the expression is multiplied by the sensitivity of the displacement field following the expression of Eq. (32).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_e} = (\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot \frac{\partial m}{\partial x_e} \cdot \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} \frac{\Lambda_{el}^3 + \Lambda_{el}}{N_{el}} \\ + \xi \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial x_e} \cdot \mathbf{U} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial x_e} \cdot \left[(\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot m_e(x) \cdot \right. \\ \left. \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} \left((3 \cdot \Lambda_{el}^2 + 1) \cdot \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{el}}{\sigma_{el}^V} \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C}_{el} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \right) / N_{el} \right. \\ \left. + \mathbf{K} \cdot \xi \right] \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

If the last term in Eq. (32) which is multiplied by the sensitivity of the displacement field is set equal to zero, then the expression of Eq. (33) is formed.

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{adjoint}}^x = \mathbf{K} \cdot \xi \quad (33)$$

where the adjoint loading vector $\mathbf{F}_{\text{adjoint}}^x$ is set equal to the expression of Eq. (34).

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_{\text{adjoint}}^x = -(\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot m_e(x) \cdot \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} \left[(3 \cdot \Lambda_{el}^2 + 1) \cdot \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{el}}{\sigma_{el}^V} \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C}_{el} \right. \\ \left. \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \right] / N_{el} \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Therefore, the final form of the sensitivity of the penalty function P follows the expression of Eq. (35).

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_e} = (\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot \frac{\partial m}{\partial x_e} \cdot \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} (\Lambda_{el}^3 + \Lambda_{el}) / N_{el} + \xi \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial x_e} \cdot \mathbf{U} \quad (35)$$

Moving to the sensitivity of the penalty function P with respect to material densities y , the form follows the expression of Eq. (36).

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial y_{el}} = \sum_{e=1}^N \left[(\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot \frac{\partial h}{\partial y_{el}} \right] \quad (36)$$

where, similar to Eq. (27), the term $\partial h / \partial y_{el}$ is obtained following the expression of Eq. (37). The sensitivity of the constraint function g_e with respect to y is presented in detail in Fig. A.

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial y_{el}} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial y_{el}} = m_e \cdot (3 \cdot \Lambda_{el}^2 + 1) / N_{el} \cdot \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial y_{el}} \quad (37)$$

The sensitivity of $\partial \Lambda / \partial y_{el}$ is obtained following the expression of Eq. (38).

$$\frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial y_{el}} = \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\sigma^V} \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \cdot \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \mathbf{U}_e + \mathbf{C}_{el} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial y_{el}} \right] \quad (38)$$

To remove the term $\partial \mathbf{U} / \partial y_{el}$, the adjoint method is again implemented. Using the adjoint method, the sensitivity of the penalty function is modified following the expression of Eq. (39).

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial y_{el}} = \sum_{e=1}^N \left[(\lambda_e^k + \mu^k \cdot h_e(x, y)) \cdot \frac{\partial h}{\partial y_{el}} \right] + \xi \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{K} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial y_{el}} \right) \quad (39)$$

By replacing the term $\partial h / \partial y_{el}$, the new form of Eq. (39) follows the expression of Eq. (40).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial P}{\partial y_{el}} = \sum_{e=1}^N \left[(\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot m_e \cdot (3 \cdot \Lambda_{el}^2 + 1) / N_{el} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\sigma^V} \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \cdot \right. \\ \left. \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \mathbf{U}_e + \mathbf{C}_{el} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial y_{el}} \right] \right] \\ + \xi \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{K} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial y_{el}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

Rearranging the terms of Eq. (40), the two main parts of the expression are formed as expressed in Eq. (41).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial P}{\partial y_{el}} = \sum_{e=1}^N \left\{ (\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot m_e \cdot (3 \cdot \Lambda_{el}^2 + 1) \cdot \frac{1}{N_{el}} \right. \\ \left. \cdot \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\sigma^V} \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \mathbf{U}_e \right\} \\ + \xi \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot \mathbf{U} \\ + \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot \left\{ \sum_{e=1}^N (\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot m_e \cdot (3 \cdot \Lambda_{el}^2 + 1) \cdot \frac{1}{N_{el}} \right. \\ \left. \cdot \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\sigma^V} \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e + \mathbf{K} \cdot \xi \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

The second part (the part that is multiplied by the displacement sensitivities) can be isolated and set equal to zero. This creates the expression of Eq. (42),

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{adjoint}}^y = \mathbf{K} \cdot \xi \quad (42)$$

where the adjoint loading vector is obtained following the expression of Eq. (43):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_{\text{adjoint}}^y = - \sum_{e=1}^N (\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot m_e \cdot (3 \cdot \Lambda_{el}^2 + 1) \cdot \frac{1}{N_{el}} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\sigma^V} \\ \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

Having removed the zero term of Eq. (41), the final form of the sensitivity of the penalty function is formulated following the expression of Eq. (44).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial P(x, y)}{\partial y_{el}} = \sum_{e=1}^N \left[(\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot m_e \cdot (3 \cdot \Lambda_{el}^2 + 1) \cdot \frac{1}{N_{el}} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\sigma^V} \right. \\ \left. \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \right. \\ \left. \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \mathbf{U}_e \right] + \xi \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot \mathbf{U} \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

4.2. Final gradient expressions for optimization

Combining all previous components, the complete gradient of the augmented Lagrangian functional is presented in the expressions of Eq. (45) and (46). These expressions are ready for integration into a numerical optimization algorithm.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial x} = \frac{A_e}{\sum_{e=1}^{N_e} A_e} + \frac{1}{N} \cdot \left[(\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot \frac{\partial m}{\partial x_e} \cdot \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} \frac{\Lambda_{el}^3 + \Lambda_{el}}{N_{el}} + \xi \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial x_e} \cdot \mathbf{U} \right] \quad (45)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial y_{el}} &= \frac{A_{el}}{\sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} A_{el}} + \frac{1}{N} \cdot \left[\sum_{e=1}^N (\lambda_e + \mu \cdot h_e) \cdot m_e \cdot (3 \cdot \Lambda^2 + 1) \cdot \frac{1}{N_{el}} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\sigma^V} \right. \\ &\quad \cdot \sigma_{\text{lim}}^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial C}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \mathbf{U}_e \\ &\quad \left. + \xi \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot \mathbf{U} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

The sensitivities of the volume and penalty functions complete the formulation required for updating both macroscopic and microscopic material densities within the optimization procedure. Using the adjoint method, the computational burden associated with displacement sensitivities is significantly reduced, making the procedure scalable for large-scale problems. The resulting expressions maintain full fidelity to the stress constraints at each scale and are compatible with standard gradient-based optimization solvers. This comprehensive sensitivity analysis ensures that the multiscale topology optimization framework remains robust, efficient, and capable of producing structurally sound designs that adhere to strict stress limitations.

The Augmented Lagrangian function described in (18) can easily be extended to add a volume inequality constraint following the expression of Eq. (47).

$$\begin{aligned} P(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \lambda) &= \sum_{e=1}^N \left[\lambda_e^k h_e(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) + \frac{\mu^k}{2} h_e(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})^2 \right] \\ &\quad + \eta^k V_f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) + \frac{\beta^k}{2} (\max(0, V_f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})))^2 \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Where the terms η, β denote the Lagrangian multipliers for the volume constraint and $V_f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ denotes the volume constraint. The terms η, β are updated following the same expressions as in λ, μ . More specifically, η is updated following the expression of Eq. (22), with the term h replaced by the term V_f . The term β is updated following the expression of (21). The volume constraint is calculated following the expression of Eq. (48).

$$V_f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = V(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) - f \quad (48)$$

Where $V(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ is the volume fraction of the domain and f is the volume fraction limit. The sensitivity of the additional terms of the penalty function is easily computed using the sensitivity of the volume functions presented in (24) and (25).

A flow chart of the optimization procedure is presented in Fig. 3.

As presented in the flowchart. There are two main optimization loops. The first loop consists of the two scale optimization problem, whereas, the second loop consists of the update of the Lagrange parameters. This is again inspired by the work of [7], Where the Lagrangian parameters were not updated at every optimization loop to stabilize the optimization procedure. In the flow chart the main optimization loop is presented in the right column. The steps of the optimization procedure are as presented seven. In the first step the SIMP interpolation scheme is performed. Using SIMP the macro and micro material densities x, y are translated into material properties. In the second step, the homogenization procedure is performed. With the use of homogenization the material properties of the periodic unit cell are translated to material properties of the porous domain. Using these homogenized material properties the third step is performed, the finite element analysis. In the fourth step the volume and stress constraints are calculated using the results of the previous step. In the next step objective and constraint function are combined into the Augmented Lagrangian function and in the seventh step the sensitivity analysis of the Augmented Lagrangian is performed. Finally, In the last step of the optimization procedure, the Method of Moving Asymptotes (MMA) is used to provide the procedure with the new set of material densities for both scales.

5. Numerical experiments and results

In this section, two 2D benchmark problems are used to demonstrate the capabilities of the proposed multiscale stress-based topology optimization framework. For each test case, optimized geometries for the classic stress based formulation as well as the proposed methodology are presented. In the proposed methodology, both the macro- and microscales are presented side by side. The first test case investigates the classical Messerschmitt-Bölkow-Blohm (MBB) beam configuration, while the second explores a simple beam geometry.

Fig. 3. Schematic flowchart of the optimization procedure.

5.1. MBB Test case

The first benchmark problem considers the classical Messerschmitt-Bölkow-Blohm (MBB) beam configuration. The design domain is a rectangular region with a 3:1 aspect ratio, measuring 3 m in length and 1 m in height. A concentrated vertical load of 1 MN is applied at the top-right edge of the domain to simulate structural loading. The microstructure within the macro domain is represented by periodically distributed unit cells, each modeled as a rectangular cell with dimensions of 10 cm. A detailed schematic of the MBB problem setup, including boundary and loading conditions, is provided in Fig. 4.

The MBB domain was discretized using a structured grid consisting of 250×80 finite elements along the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. Each periodic unit cell embedded within the macrostructure was discretized with a finer mesh of 30×30 finite elements to ensure an accurate resolution of microstructural features. The base material was assumed to be linearly elastic with a Young’s modulus of 70 GPa and a Poisson’s ratio of 0.25, while the allowable Von Mises stress was limited to a limit of 100 MPa.

For the optimization setup, the initial material density in the macrostructure was uniformly set to 0.5. The initial geometry of the periodic unit cell consisted of a solid matrix (density = 1) containing a central circular void with a radius equal to one-third of the unit cell’s side length, where the material density was set to zero; while SIMP method was employed with a penalty factor of 3.5. The maximum number of optimization iterations was fixed at 150, with Lagrange multipliers updated every 5 iterations. The convergence of the optimization process was declared when the relative change in the objective function fell below a tolerance threshold of 0.002. To avoid obtaining a completely solid unit cell by the end of the procedure, a volume constraint of 0.85 was set for the volume of the unit cell. The number of design variables is equal to 20,000 for the macro scale and 900 for the micro scale, therefore, 20,900 in total.

The resulting optimal geometries are presented in Fig. 5.

The optimal volume fractions for both classic and multiscale approaches are similar. For the classic approach, the optimal volume fraction is equal to 12.3%, while the optimal value of the volume fraction for the macro domain is equal to 13% and the optimal

Fig. 4. Dimensions and Boundary conditions of the MBB domain.

(a) Classic stress based TO approach

(b) Multiscale approach

Fig. 5. MBB beam optimization results for both the classic and multiscale approaches.

value of the volume fraction for the micro domain is equal to 85% as determined by the volume constraint. The maximum value of the fraction of the Von Mises stress to stress limit for each finite element of the macrodomain e for both the classic and multiscale approaches is presented in Fig. 6.

The stress distribution in terms of Von Mises stress to stress limit in the periodic unit cell is presented in Fig. 7. More specifically, the following figure shows the maximum ratio of Von Mises stress to the stress limit for each finite element of the periodic unit cell for optimal geometry.

5.2. Simple beam test case

In the simple beam test case, a domain of 3m in length and 1m in height was considered. the loading condition consisted of a concentrated load of 1MN was set at the bottom-left edge of the domain. The dimensions of the periodic unit cell are equal to a rectangle of 10cm. A schematic representation of the simple beam test case is presented in detail in Fig. 4. (Fig. 8)

(a) Classic stress based TO approach

(b) Stress distribution of micro stress projected on the macro domain for the MBB beam

Fig. 6. MBB beam optimization results for both the classic and multiscale approaches.

The simple beam domain was discretized by a grid of 225×75 finite elements in the directions of the abscissa and ordinate directions, respectively, while the periodic unit cell is discretized by a grid of 30×30 finite elements in the abscissa and ordinate directions, respectively. Regarding material properties, a material with Young Modulus equal to $70GPa$ and Poisson's ratio of 0.25 and a Von Mises stress limit of $100MPa$ was chosen. Regarding the optimization parameters, the initial material densities for the macro scale were set equal to 0.5 while the geometry of the periodic unit cell was set as a solid unit cell with material densities of 1 with a circular whole at its center with a radius of $1/3$ of its dimensions where the material densities were set equal to 0 . The penalty factor was set equal to 3.5 , the maximum number of optimization iterations equal to 150 , the iterations between the Lagrange parameter update equal to 5 and the tolerance of the optimization procedure equal to 0.002 . To avoid obtaining a completely solid unit cell by the end of the procedure, a volume constraint of 0.85 was set for the volume of the unit cell. The number of design variables are $16,875$ for the macro scale and 900 for the micro scale, therefore $17,775$ in total.

The resulting optimal geometries are presented in Fig. 9.

Fig. 7. Periodic unit cell maximum stress ratio.

Fig. 8. Dimensions and Boundary conditions of the simple beam domain.

(a) Classic stress based TO approach

(b) Multiscale approach

Fig. 9. Simple beam optimization results for both the classic and multiscale approaches.

(a) Classic stress based TO approach

(b) Stress distribution of micro stress projected on the macro domain for the MBB beam

Fig. 10. simple beam stress optimization results for both the classic and multiscale approaches.

Fig. 11. Periodic unit cell maximum stress ratio.

Similarly to the previous test case the optimal volume fractions are similar with the classic approach achieving a volume fraction of 12.6% and the multiscale approach achieving a volume fraction for the macro domain is equal to 15%, while the optimal value of the volume fraction for the micro domain is equal to 85% determined from the volume constraint. The maximum value of the fraction of the Von Mises stress to stress limit for each finite element e for both the classic and multiscale approaches is presented in Fig. 10.

The stress distribution in terms of Von Mises stress to stress limit in the periodic unit cell is presented in Fig. 11. More specifically, the following figure shows the maximum ratio of Von Mises stress to the stress limit for each finite element of the periodic unit cell for optimal geometry.

6. Conclusions and future directions

This work presented an aggregation-free, concurrent multiscale topology optimization framework for stress-constrained design. Local stress limits are enforced at the microscale through an augmented Lagrangian (AL) formulation with polynomial vanishing constraints, while macro- and micro-level material distributions are updated within a unified SIMP setting. A single adjoint problem suffices to compute the sensitivities with respect to all design variables, which makes the approach scalable even when every macro element carries a local stress constraint.

In general, enforcing stress constraints locally at the microscale within a concurrent multiscale AL framework yields stress-robust and material-efficient designs without resorting to stress aggregation. In the presented formulation, a single unit cell geometry is repeated throughout the domain. This results in a constraint on the algorithm during the optimization procedure and presented the need to apply a volume constraint to avoid the creation of solid optimal unit cell geometry. In future work, we expect to enhance the implementation of the formulation with different methodologies to apply varying unit cell geometries throughout the domain. In addition, a bi-/multi-material can further enhance the performance of the optimization procedure and widen the range of engineering applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

George Kazakis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization; **Nikos D. Lagaros:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Declaration of competing interest

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The authors whose names are listed immediately below certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent-licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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Appendix A. Sensitivity Derivation for Constraint Functions

The sensitivity analysis of the stress constraint is performed for both scales. For the macro-scale the sensitivity of the stress constraint is derived following the expression of Eq. (A.1).

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial x_e} = \frac{\partial m}{\partial x_e} \cdot \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} (\Lambda_{el}^3 + \Lambda_{el}) / N_{el} + m_e(x) \cdot \sum_{el=1}^{N_{el}} \left[(3 \cdot \Lambda_{el}^2 + 1) \cdot \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial x_e} \right] / N_{el} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $\partial m / \partial x$ is derived following the expression of Eq. (A.2):

$$\frac{\partial m}{\partial x_e} = p \cdot x_e^{p-1} \cdot (1 - x_{min}) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Additionally, term $\partial \Lambda / \partial x$ is derived following the expression of Eq. (A.3):

$$\frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial x_e} = \frac{\partial \sigma^V}{\partial x_e} \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where $\partial \sigma^V / \partial x$ derives from the expression of Eq. (A.4):

$$\frac{\partial \sigma^V}{\partial x_e} = \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{el}}{\sigma_{el}^V} \cdot \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\partial x_e} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The derivative of the stress vector follows the expression of Eq. (A.5):

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\partial x_e} = \mathbf{C}_{el} \cdot \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{el}}{\partial x_e} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where the sensitivity of the strain vector derives following the expression of Eq. (A.6):

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{el}}{\partial x_e} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \boldsymbol{\chi}) \cdot \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_e}{\partial x_e} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Finally, the sensitivity of the macro strain field follows the expression of Eq (A.7):

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_e}{\partial x_e} = \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial x_e} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

For the micro scale the sensitivity of the stress constraint is derived following the expression of Eq. (A.8).

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial y_{el}} = m_e \cdot (3 \cdot \Lambda^2 + 1) / N_{el} \cdot \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial y_{el}} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

The term $\partial \Lambda / \partial y_{el}$ follows the expression of Eq. (A.9).

$$\frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial y_{el}} = \frac{\partial \sigma^V}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot \sigma_{lim}^{-1} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

The term $\partial \sigma^V / \partial y_{el}$ follows the expression of Eq. (A.10).

$$\frac{\partial \sigma^V}{\partial y_{el}} = \frac{\mathbf{V}_0 \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{el}}{\sigma_{el}^V} \cdot \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\partial y_{el}} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

where the sensitivity of the stress field follows the expression of Eq (A.11).

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}{\partial y_{el}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{el} + \mathbf{C} \cdot \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{el}}{\partial y_{el}} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where the term $\partial \mathbf{C} / \partial y_{el}$ follows the expression of Eq. (A.12).

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}}{\partial y_{el}} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial y_{el}} \cdot \mathbf{C}^0 \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where the term $\partial E / \partial y_{el}$ follows the expression of Eq. (A.13).

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial y_{el}} = p \cdot y^{p-1} \cdot (E^0 - E_{min}) \quad (\text{A.13})$$

Additionally, the sensitivity of the micro strain field follows the expression of Eq. (A.14).

$$\frac{\partial \epsilon_{el}}{\partial y_{el}} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_{el} \cdot \chi) \cdot \frac{\partial \epsilon_e}{\partial y_{el}} \quad (\text{A.14})$$

The sensitivity of the macro strain field is following the expression of Eq. (A.15).

$$\frac{\partial \epsilon_e}{\partial y_{el}} = \mathbf{B}_e \cdot \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial y_{el}} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

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